

Computational study of inclusion complexation of sulphanilamide drugs with β -cyclodextrin

A. Antony Muthu Prabhu and N. Rajendiran*

Department of Chemistry, Annamalai University, Annamalaiagar-608 002, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : drrajendiran@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-4144-238080

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Abstract : The inclusion process involving sulfisoxazole (SFO), sulfamethoxazole (SMO), sulfathiazole (STO) and sulfanilamide (SAM) with β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) were investigated by PM3 method. The quantum computational methods gave the most favorable structure in which the guest molecule partially embedded in the hydrophobic cavity of the cyclodextrin. The aniline moiety located near the primary hydroxyls of the β -CD and the heterocyclic ring near the secondary hydroxyls with hydrogen bonding formation. The difference in complexation energy confirmed that SAM formed a more stable complex with β -CD than the other molecules. The negative complexation energies suggested that the inclusion complexes are stable. HOMO and LUMO orbital investigations confirmed the better stability of the inclusion complexes.

Keywords : Sulphanilamides, cyclodextrin, inclusion complexation, PM3, molecular modeling.

Introduction

Cyclodextrins (CDs) can form inclusion complexes with many compounds¹⁻¹⁴. CD chemistry has caused much interest, not only due to its applications in pharmaceutical science and separation technology, but also because the inclusion represents an ideal model mimicking enzyme-substrate interactions. CD inclusion complexes are also valuable models for understanding non-covalent intermolecular interactions¹⁻¹⁴.

The driving forces leading to the complexation are important in CD chemistry³, which have been studied theoretically with quantum mechanical or molecular mechanical calculation¹⁵, linear regression¹⁶ and artificial neural networks¹⁷. The driving forces have been attributed to factors including van der Waals force, hydrophobic effect and dipole-dipole interactions¹⁸. Quantitative models based on this theory⁵⁻⁸ could well account for the observed trends in binding energy in general.

Among the different families of organic and inorganic chemicals being currently investigated for their applications, sulfonamides and their *N*-derivatives are one of the outstanding groups. Sulfonamides were the first effective chemotherapeutic agents employed systematically for the prevention and cure of bacterial infections in humans. After the introduction of penicillin and other antibiotics,

the popularity of sulfonamides decreased. However, they are still considered useful in certain therapeutic fields, especially in the case of ophthalmic infections as well as infections in the urinary and gastrointestinal tract. Even today, sulfa drugs are among the drugs of first selections (together with ampicillin and gentamycin) as chemotherapeutic agents in bacterial infections by *Escherichia coli* in humans. The sulfanilamides exert their antibacterial action by the competitive inhibition of the enzyme dihydropterase synthetase towards the substrate *p*-aminobenzoate.

Herein, we studied the quantum chemistry calculations for sulphanilamide drugs with β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) which have been shown to be reliable in the modeling of CD complexation^{19,20}. Due to difficulties in modeling the solvation effect, only the gas phase interaction between the host and guest was evaluated. The results of the gas-phase calculations were compared and analysed with experimental results with the following points in the mind : (1) the effect of solvation on the complexation of CD with guests and (2) whether the dipole-dipole interaction does favor the complexation with the guest molecules or not. It was observed that the calculation gave larger complexation energy for the guest compounds and investigations were made for what factor leads to such a result.

The reason for choosing sulfisoxazole (SFO, N^1 -(3,4-dimethyl-5-isoxazolyl)sulfanilamide), sulfamethoxazole (SMO, N^1 -(5-methyl-3-isoxazolyl)sulfanilamide), sulfathiazole (STO, N^1 -(2-thiazolyl)sulfanilamide) and sulfanilamide (SAM, 4-aminobenzene sulfonamide) (Fig. 1) is that these drugs are quite large and thus it will encapsulate only partially to the β -CD cavity. In our recent publications we experimentally proved that the above molecules formed 1 : 1 inclusion complex with β -CD^{19,20}. Sulphonamides belong to the group of antibacterial drugs, which are used for human and animal therapy, to cure infectious diseases of digestive and respiratory systems, affections of the skin (in the form of ointments) and for prevention or therapy of coccidiosis of small domestic animals.

Materials and methods :

All the theoretical calculations were performed with Gaussian 03W. The initial geometry of the drugs and β -CD were constructed with Spartan 08 and then optimized by PM3. β -CD was fully optimized by PM3 without any symmetry constraint²¹. The glycosidic oxygen atoms of CD were placed onto the XY plane and their center was defined as the center of the coordination system. The primary hydroxyl groups were placed pointing toward the positive Z axis. The inclusion complexes were constructed from the PM3-optimized β -CD and guest molecules. The NH_2 group was always located pointing to the primary hydroxyls of β -CD according to the experimental observation^{19,20}. The longer dimension of the guest molecule was initially placed onto the Z axis. The posi-

Fig. 1. The optimized structure of (a) SFO, (b) SMO, (c) STO and (d) SAM.

tion of the guest was determined by the Z coordinate of one selected atom of the guest. The inclusion process was simulated by putting the guest in one end of β -CD and then letting it pass through the β -CD cavity. Since the semiempirical PM3 method has been proved to be a powerful tool in the conformational study of cyclodextrin complexes and has high computational efficiency in calculating the CDs systems²²⁻²⁴, it was selected to study the inclusion process of β -CD with the sulpha drugs in this paper.

Results and discussion

HOMO-LUMO parameters :

The energy, HOMO, LUMO, thermodynamic parameters (enthalpy, entropy, free energy), chemical potential (μ), stability (S), dipole moment (D), hardness (η), electrophilicity (ω), zero point vibrational energy and Mulliken charge of the guest (SFO, SMO, STO and SAM), host (β -CD) and inclusion complexes are summarized in Table 1. From Fig. 2, it can be seen that the guest molecules formed stable inclusion complexes with β -CD. Interestingly, it was observed that the structure of the above four drug: β -CD inclusion complexes were very similar to each other. The structural similarity could be a factor

that made the complexation energies of β -CD with the four guest molecules same.

HOMO as ionization energy (IE) and LUMO as electron affinity (EA) were used for calculating the electronic chemical potential (μ) which is half of the energy of the HOMO and LUMO :

$$\mu = (E_{\text{HOMO}} + E_{\text{LUMO}})/2 \quad (1)$$

The hardness (η) as half of the gap energy between HOMO and LUMO was calculated using the following expression :

$$\text{Gap} = E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}} \quad (2)$$

$$\eta = E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}}/2 \quad (3)$$

The electrophilicity (ω) of the components were calculated in PM3 method using the following equation :

$$\omega = \mu^2/2\eta \quad (4)$$

From Table 1, it was found that, (i) chemical potential and HOMO of SMO were more negative whereas electrophilicity of SMO was more positive than that of SFO, STO and SAM, (ii) dipole and hardness of SAM were larger than that of other three drugs, (iii) HOMO-LUMO gap for SAM was higher than other drugs, (iv) chemical potential of SAM: β -CD was less negative than that of

Table 1. Binding energies and HOMO-LUMO calculations for the inclusion complexes using PM3 method

Properties	SFO	SMO	STO	SAM	β -CD	SFO: β -CD	SMO: β -CD	STO: β -CD	SAM: β -CD
E_{HOMO} (eV)	-8.99	-9.39	-9.17	-9.29	-10.35	-8.89	-8.86	-8.76	-8.73
E_{LUMO} (eV)	-0.91	-0.90	-0.95	-0.65	1.23	-0.78	-0.70	-0.81	-0.42
$E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$ (eV)	-8.08	-8.49	-8.22	-8.63	-11.58	-8.11	-8.16	-7.96	-8.31
μ	-4.95	-5.14	-5.06	-4.97	-4.56	-4.83	-4.78	-4.78	-4.57
η	4.04	4.24	4.11	4.32	5.79	4.06	4.08	3.98	4.15
ω	3.03	3.11	3.11	2.85	1.79	2.87	2.80	2.86	2.51
S	0.25	0.23	0.24	0.23	0.17	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.24
Dipole (D)	5.09	7.02	5.38	7.48	12.29	5.32	6.46	8.87	10.07
ΔD						-12.06	-12.85	-8.8	-9.7
E (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-22.95	-14.87	3.71	-10.76	-1457.63	-1487.59	-1476.32	-1460.44	-1516.52
ΔE (kcal mol ⁻¹)						-7.01	-3.82	-6.52	-48.13
G (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-116.05	-99.26	-81.37	-64.15	-667.55	-802.12	-783.49	-766.83	-746.92
ΔG (kcal mol ⁻¹)						-18.52	-16.68	-17.91	-15.22
H (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-157.82	-139.93	-120.34	-95.47	-789.52	-949.63	-930.55	-910.99	-886.54
ΔH (kcal mol ⁻¹)						-2.29	-1.1	-1.13	-1.55
S (kcal/mol-Kelvin)	-0.1401	-0.1364	-0.1296	-0.1050	-0.4091	-0.4947	-0.4933	-0.4835	-0.4683
ΔS (kcal/mol-Kelvin)						-0.0545	-0.0523	-0.0553	-0.0459
Zero point vibrational energy	146.18	128.91	109.94	87.82	740.56	888.53	870.10	851.80	829.57
Mulliken properties	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Fig. 2. Axial and equatorial views of low energy structures calculated for the complexes between β -CD and (a) SFO, (b) SMO, (c) STO and (d) SAM.

SFO, STO and SAM inclusion complexes, (v) dipole and the HOMO-LUMO gap for SAM inclusion complex were larger than the other three complexes, (vi) no marginal

difference was observed in the stability of the four drugs and their complexes, (vii) high negative ΔE was noticed in the SAM: β -CD inclusion complexes, (viii) electronic

energy, Gibbs free energy, enthalpy and entropy of SFO was more negative than other drugs and (ix) entropy values for all the drugs and the inclusion complexes were negative.

The chemical potential of all the inclusion complexes were negative indicating all the inclusion process were spontaneous. However, SFO:β-CD inclusion complex showed more negative value than other complexes suggesting this complexation process was more spontaneous than other complexes. The HOMO-LUMO value of the SAM:β-CD inclusion complex was slightly higher than other three inclusion complexes.

The ($E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$) gap is an important scale of stability²⁵ and compounds with large ($E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$) values tend to have higher stability. So, we investigated the electronic structure of the complexes in with these considerations using PM3 method. The HOMO-LUMO energy gap of these drugs and their inclusion complexes were calculated using PM3 and are shown in Table 1 and Fig. 3, which revealed that the energy gap reflected the chemical activity of the molecules. The LUMO as an electron acceptor represents the ability to obtain an electron and HOMO represents the ability to donate electron. Moreover, a lower HOMO-LUMO energy gap explained the eventual stability of the complex i.e. isolated molecule had lower stability than complex molecule. The $E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$ gap (Table 1) confirmed that the stability of the drug - β-CD inclusion complexes were more stable.

Fig. 3 indicated that the HOMO-LUMO energy gaps of all these complexes were significantly varied. The energy gap between HOMO and LUMO of each complex suggested a significant change in the electronic spectrum of the guest molecules driving molecular recognition and binding. This suggested the stability of these inclusion complexes were same. The HOMO of these drugs was slightly varied (Table 1 and Fig. 3) indicating inclusion complexation processes differ from each other. The HOMO-LUMO gap for SAM:β-CD inclusion complex was more negative suggesting this complex is more stable than other three drug:β-CD inclusion complexes.

The dipole of SAM was higher than that of SMO, STO and SFO. The dipole moment of the drugs and the inclusion complexes were present in the following order :

β-CD > SAM:β-CD > STO:β-CD > SMO:β-CD > SFO:β-CD > SAM > SMO > STO > SFO. The dipole moment of the β-CD is 12.29 D, SAM:β-CD is 10.07 D, STO:β-CD is 8.87 D, SMO:β-CD is 6.46 D, SFO:β-CD is 5.32 D, SAM is 7.48 D, SMO is 7.02 D, STO is 5.38 D, SFO is 5.09 D. The inclusion complexes dipoles were higher than isolated drugs where as lower than β-CD. This was because, the polarity of the β-CD cavity decreased after the drug entered the cavity. The above quantum mechanical computations demonstrated a strong relationship with the complexation behavior. One can therefore conclude the dipole moment values having a strong a correlation with the complexation behaviour. However, it is not straight forward why the complexation of β-CD with SAM is more favorable than other drugs if the dipole-dipole interaction and hydrophobic interaction are the only driving forces in β-CD complexation.

Though the results are not readily understandable, the Morokuma theory of energy decomposition analysis²⁶ can offer a reasonable explanation. According to the theory, when a supermolecule was formed, electrons will lose their identity as belonging to one or other component molecule. Four types of interactions should be considered in the formation of a supermolecule : (a) electrostatic interaction, which is favored by large permanent charges and dipoles, (b) polarization interaction, which is favored by large volume and polarizability of the molecules, (c) exchange energy, or Pauli repulsion and (d) charge-transfer interaction, which is resulted from the mixing of the filled orbital of one component molecule with the vacant orbital of the other. The charge-transfer interaction is always attractive and the most important terms in this interaction are contributed from the charge-transfer between the HOMO of one component and the LUMO of the other. The first three interactions constitute the canonical driving forces in CD chemistry, i.e. dipole-dipole interaction, dipole-induced dipole interaction and steric effect. However, they cannot explain the unexpected theoretical and experimental observations. The higher the HOMO of the guest molecule, the stronger is the charge-transfer interaction in the complexation. Here, the quantum mechanical studies indicate that no charge-transfer interactions are present in the four drugs with β-CD. Mulliken charge values for all the four complexes were zero, confirmed no charge transfer interactions are

Fig. 3. The HOMO, LUMO energy structure of (a) SFO, (b) SMO, (c) STO and (d) SAM.

present in the β -CD complexation. Interestingly, β -CD is ready to act as Lewis acid accepting electrons, but the sulphonamide guests do not act as Lewis bases donating electrons. Thus, no charge transfer interactions are present between the HOMO of the drug compounds and the LUMO of β -CD.

Thermodynamics parameters :

To investigate the thermodynamics of the inclusion process, the binding energies (ΔE), Gibbs energy changes (ΔG), enthalpy changes (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS) for the most stable inclusion complexes were calculated and summarized in Table 1. The complexation energy allowed us to evaluate the inclusion process and to find

the most stable inclusion complex between the complexes studied. It was evaluated as

$$\Delta E_{\text{complexation}} = E_{\text{complex}} - (E_{\beta\text{-CD}} + E_{\text{drug}}) \quad (5)$$

where E_{complex} , $E_{\beta\text{-CD}}$ and E_{drug} represent the total energy of the complex, the free optimized β -CD and the free optimized drugs respectively. All the complexation energies were more negative than isolated drugs and β -CD. The lowest values for complexation energy correspond to the most stable complex. The higher binding energy (ΔE) of the complexes suggested that stability of complex is more compared to isolated molecule. The energy for the isolated STO was slightly positive whereas negative values observed for the other three drugs. The complexation energies, enthalpies, free energies and en-

tropies were negative for all the four complexes which demonstrated that the inclusion processes were thermodynamically favorable. Among the four inclusion complexes, the energy of SAM:β-CD inclusion complex has lowest energy ($-48.13 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) when compared to SFO:β-CD ($-7.01 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$), STO:β-CD ($-6.52 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) and SMO:β-CD ($-3.82 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$). This indicated that SAM and β-CD form more stable inclusion complex than other drugs. The experimental complexation energies were significantly varied from theoretical (SFO : $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim 418 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 623 \text{ mol}^{-1}$; SMO : $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim 350 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 546 \text{ mol}^{-1}$; STO : $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim 325 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 524 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and SAM : $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim 287 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 434 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)^{19,20}.

The energy involved in hydrogen bond interaction is also responsible for the higher/lower binding energy compared to those of the substituted/unsubstituted molecules. The difference in ΔE for SAM:β-CD inclusion complexes indicated that the interactions of hydrogen atoms of SAM with β-CD are much stronger than other complexes. From Table 1 and Fig. 2, marginal variations were noticed in ΔE for SAM:β-CD inclusion complex. This confirmed that hydrogen bonding interaction played significant roles in the complexation process. These results confirmed that, the polar $-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}-$ substituent of these drugs was located near the wider end of the β-CD cavity, and SAM is deeply included in the CD cavity than other drugs. Hence ' ΔE ' value the SAM inclusion complex is higher than that of other drug complexes. The ' ΔE ' values are a reasonable measure of hydrogen bonding and the change in hydrogen bonding of the drugs are caused only by the hydrogen ion concentrations. From the Fig. 2, we also found that the above four drugs were partially included in the β-CD cavity.

The free energy, enthalpy and entropy for the inclusion complexes were more negative than that of isolated drug and β-CD. The negative free energy change (ΔG) of the inclusion complexes suggest that the inclusion proceeded spontaneously at 303 K. The theoretical ΔG values were (SFO : $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim -18.52$; SMO : $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim -16.68$; STO : $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim -17.91$; SAM : $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim -15.22 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) were different from experimental (unit : kcal mol^{-1} , SFO : $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim -15.21$, $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim -16.20$; SMO : $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim -14.76$, $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim -15.87$; STO : $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim -14.56$, $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim -15.76$; SAM : $\lambda_{\text{abs}} \sim -14.26$, $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim -15.29$). The high negative ΔG value for

SFO:β-CD inclusion complex indicated that this inclusion process is more spontaneous than other complexes.

The difference in ΔE and ΔG can be explained by the solvent effect. The experiments are conducted in aqueous medium and the computational work was done at vacuum phase. We were unable to do the computational work at the aqueous medium due to system limitation. Due to the large molecular size of β-CD, calculations for these systems could not be performed for aqueous solutions and excited state. However, it was observed that the solvent effect on the host-guest interactions easily changed the inclusion reaction from a non-spontaneous process in the gas phase to a spontaneous one in the aqueous phase. The host-guest interaction causes an enthalpy-entropy compensating process in the gas phase whereas the same interaction caused an enthalpy-entropy co-driven process in aqueous solution, because inclusion complexation releases a number of water molecules from the cavity of β-CD.

Recently, some authors who encountered this discrepancy used the experimental values to modify their calculations. For example in the case of the complexes of both *cis* and *trans* isomers of Brooker's mercyanine inserted within β-CD cavity, the author's preliminary calculations of ΔG values predicted the complex would not form spontaneously and the magnitude and the sign of ΔS and ΔG values varied from the experiment values¹⁸. They argued that, experimentally the entropy of complexation depends on both the insertion of the drug molecule and the concurrent displacement of water molecules that are trapped within the β-CD cavity. The water molecule should be included in the calculations and then they found the thermodynamic values closer to the experimental results and the sign matched the reported values in all cases. Further Xing *et al.*⁶ proposed a model to calculate ΔS for the inclusion complex in aqueous solution with the assumptions that the effect of water molecules on the entropy changes of the 2-hydroxy-5-methoxyacetophenone:β-CD system is mainly determined by the water molecules in the β-CD cavity and the effect of the H₂O molecules out of the cavity is less important and thus can be negligible.

The very small negative ΔH values indicated that the inclusion formations of drugs with β-CD are an exothermic and enthalpy-driven $\Delta H > \Delta S$. It should be noted that ΔH and ΔS values contain contributions from (i) re-

lease of cavity found water, (ii) partial destruction of hydration shells of the reagents, (iii) non-covalent interactions (van der Waals, hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions as well as hydrogen bonding) and (iv) hydration of the complexes. All these process should be taken into account while discussing thermodynamic parameters of complex formation.

SFO is bounds to β -CD with more negative ΔH than other drug complexes. Probably geometric factor plays a considerable role in this complexation process. The small negative ΔS is a confirmed the restriction of freedom of the molecule and formation of less compact structures. As it is evident from Table 1, hydroxyl groups reduce binding affinity of β -CD to drugs, making the complexation process more enthalpy and less entropy favourable. It is assumed that the β -CD cavity size and drugs substituents serve as a steric hindrance for the drug inclusion.

The small negative ΔS values were assumed to be due to enhancement of disorder in the system. Moreover hydrophobic interactions, which are long range interactions, can be important in the β -CD complex formation. The inclusion complex structure in Fig. 2 also suggested that benzene ring was partially include the cavity and interacts with it through hydrophobic interactions. Further the small ΔH values can be explained by the prevalence of hydrophobic interactions. Comparison of ΔH and ΔS showed that enthalpy changes are higher and entropy changes are lower for the complexation. Therefore complexes of the drugs with β -CD are more enthalpy stabilized.

The optimized inclusion structure in Fig. 2 showed, hydrogen bond is formed only in SAM: β -CD inclusion complex. The intermolecular hydrogen bonds were formed between hydrogen atom of amino group of the drugs and oxygen atom of primary hydroxyl group of the β -CD with a $d_{H...O}$ distance less than 3.00 Å. This justified the importance of both interaction between the drugs and β -CD necessary to ensure better inclusion of the guest to the host. The above values were supported by the fact that the flexibility of the host molecule may be one of the structural requirements for inclusion complexes formation. Though the above four drugs had similar volumes, polarizability and hydrophobicity, β -CD complexation with SAM was stronger than that of SFO, SMO and STO. The present calculation showed that hydrogen bonding in

SAM: β -CD inclusion complex brought the difference in the binding energies of β -CD complexation with other sulphanilamide drugs.

The bond distances, bond angles and the most interesting dihedral angles of the drugs before and after complexation in β -CD obtained from PM3 calculations for the most stable structure (Fig. 2) are presented in Table 2. It was evident that in β -CD the geometry of the drugs are slightly altered. The alterations were significant in dihedral angles, which indicated that the drugs adopted a specific conformation to form a stable complex. The internal diameter of β -CD is approximately 6.5 Å and the height is 7.8 Å. Considering the shape and dimensions of β -CD, the four drugs can not be completely embedded in the β -CD nano cavity. The vertical distance and length of the drugs are greater than the upper/lower rim of β -CD. Hence, the aromatic rings can not be fully present inside the β -CD nano cavity. Further, the optimized theoretical structure of drugs: β -CD inclusion complex by Gauss view method also confirmed the drugs are partially included in the β -CD nano cavity.

It is well known that the van der Waals forces including the dipole-induced dipole interactions are proportional to the distance between guest, the wall of the β -CD cavity and to the polarizabilities of the two components. The interaction of the phenyl ring with β -CD would play an important role because the phenyl moiety may achieve a maximum contact area with the internal surface of the cavity of the CD.

The above results suggested the inclusion of the drug molecules with β -CD nano cavity is affected by hydrophobic and electronic interactions. Since CD has a permanent dipole the primary hydroxyl end is positive and the secondary hydroxyl end is negative in the glucose units of CD. The stability of binding by hydrophobic interaction is partly the result of van der Waals force but is mainly due to the effects of entropy produced on the water molecules. In the aqueous solution, a hydrophobic guest compound is restricted by the water shell formed by the hydrogen bonding network. It has a strong tendency to break down the water cluster and penetrate the non-polar cavity of the CD. This process is exothermic due to entropic gain. The energy for the inclusion of CD with guest compounds were observed to be proportional to the substituent hydrophobic constant of the guest.

Table 2. Geometrical parameters of SFO, SMO, STO and SAM before and after inclusion in β -CD for the most stable inclusion complexes

Properties	SFO	SFO: β -CD	SFO: β -CD	STO	STO: β -CD	SAM: β -CD	
Bond length (Å) :							
H ₅ -H ₁₂	10.62	12.06	H ₄ -H ₁₂	11.36	10.20	H ₅ -O ₂	7.26
N ₁ -N ₃	6.97	8.48	C ₁ -C ₁₈	7.05	7.01	N ₁ -N ₂	6.60
N ₁ -S	5.90	5.95	H ₆ -O	7.07	6.99	N ₁ -S	6.00
S-H ₁₂	6.70	6.77	H ₆ -H ₂	7.48	7.42	H ₁ -H ₄	4.36
NH ₂ -OH(1°)	4.17	4.17	H ₁₀ -C ₁		3.31		2.74
NH ₂ -OH(1°)	3.45	3.45			3.69		3.52
SO ₂ -HO(1° or 2°)	1.80	1.80			4.54		2.78
SO ₂ -HO(1° or 2°)	2.51	2.51			4.62		3.74
=N...HO(2°)	4.41	4.41			2.96		
Bond angle (°) :							
S-N ₂ -C ₇	125.93	128.65	C ₁ -N ₁ -N ₂	118.35	119.00	H ₅ -N ₁ -C ₁	112.83
C ₄ -S-N ₂	105.91	102.37	C ₁₁ -N ₂ -N ₁	120.06	114.61	C ₄ -S-N ₂	100.94
							102.19
Dihedral angle (°) :							
C ₄ -S-N ₂ -C ₇	-67.95	-111.33	C ₁₁ -N ₁ -N ₂ -C ₁₁	-179.99	-170.19	H ₈ -N ₂ -S-O ₁	-175.19
C ₇ -C ₈ -C ₁₀ -C ₁₁	-179.76	179.62	O-C ₂ -C ₁ -N ₁	-0.001	-0.0012	H ₇ -N ₂ -S-O ₂	175.26
O ₂ -S-N ₂ -C ₇	51.39	7.98	N ₂ -C ₇ -N ₃ -O ₃	-30.20	-29.55	H ₇ -N ₂ -S-C ₄	-69.70
							-112.84

Conclusion :

From the above study we find out that (i) the stability of the four inclusion complexes were same, (ii) the four sulphonamide molecules were partially encapsulated in to the β -CD cavity, (iii) the negative Gibbs energy and enthalpy changes for the inclusion complexes indicated that the formation of these complexes are spontaneous and weak exothermic, (iv) hydrogen bonding interactions played a major role in the SAM: β -CD inclusion process while hydrophobic interactions were present in other inclusion complexes, (v) the dipole moment values for drugs increased when they entered into the β -CD cavity which is an indication of the increase of the polarity and the formation of complex and (vi) the computational results indicated that the formation of all the inclusion complexes were enthalpy driven process.

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